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5G SUPPLY MARKET TRENDS

Workshop Preparatory Report

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1 INTRODUCTION

The study on the 5G supply market trends, which was launched in September 2020 and has a project runtime of 11 months, aims at providing the European Commission with an in-depth analysis on qualitative and quantitative information on the 4G and 5G equipment and services supply market trends. The study provides:

- 1) a baseline assessment of the 5G equipment and services supply markets including new deployment and operation models,
- 2) an analysis of the level of maturity of past, existing and upcoming open radio access networks (RANs) and the state of play in global international standardization organizations regarding the open initiatives, in order to
- 3) define scenarios on the future development of supply market trends and
- 4) identify and analyse potential policy options facilitating a healthy development for European companies and SMEs in the evolving ecosystems.

In the first three months, the project team finalised an analysis of the current state of play of the 4G and 5G supply chain and market shares of infrastructures providers and performed the analysis of the state of play of the existing and upcoming open radio access networks.

Furthermore, the study team launched a foresight exercise in order to identify key trends influencing the development of 5G. The scenarios to be developed by those trends, will provide different visions for Europe, based on plausible different configurations of key technological, economic, social and political factors.

This document serves the purpose to inform the participants of the first stakeholder workshop of this study about the results of the analyses that have been generated in the first phase of this study.

2 MAIN MESSAGES FROM THE BASELINE ASSESSMENT

Technology developments in the fields of hardware and software disaggregation and network-function virtualization and containerization are allowing for radical architectural changes across mobile network domains. To fully reap the benefits of network virtualization, telco operators have begun to rethink sourcing and deployment models, as well as corresponding organizational set-ups. Three key market trends are acting as catalysts for the large-scale adoption of technology developments in the near future:

1. Interoperability of vendors within and between the individual network domains (RAN, transport, core and orchestration) will further develop at a rapid pace, also based on specifications developed by the O-RAN Alliance
2. As a consequence of this expansion, the vendor landscape is in a process of broadening. It contributes to the availability of competitive solutions for all network domains on the market, thereby fostering a clear paradigm shift of traditional and “new” network equipment providers (NEPs). This shift could be facilitated by the ongoing evolution from monolithic telecom network infrastructure to software-based IT solutions.
3. Technology development will soon reach a point when significant expected network TCO savings can be achieved, through establishment of an ecosystem of suitable integration partners, from which the best and cheapest technologies can be chosen in a “pick and mix” style. With TCO savings, integration efforts and risk for decoupled and disaggregated solutions will seem reasonable.

Leading operators across the globe have already taken the first steps toward these target networks, as illustrated in Figure 1. Although virtualization concepts and subsequent target network architectures still remain at early stages of development, the first live deployments – such as those by Rakuten in Japan, AT&T in the US and Telefonica in selected markets – clearly indicate improvements with regards to set-up and operating efforts over distributed/centralized network architectures across domains.

With a broadening vendor landscape, higher interoperability and promises for cost-performance improvements along the customer journey, operators might soon be able to realize network TCO savings of up to 44 percent compared to traditional distributed/centralized RAN setups, CAPEX could be reduced by up to 50 percent due

to vendor competition across domains, and OPEX savings of up to 53 percent could mainly come from efficiencies in deployment and operations, such as zero-touch automation¹.

Figure 1: Global overview of virtual RAN/ORAN deployments²

2.1 The status of 5G rollouts

On the markets, 5G Rollouts have started across the world and are beginning to reach the point of scale at which 5G can be sold as a reliable product to consumers and businesses. South Korea, China, and North America are the most advanced globally in their 5G rollouts and have begun offering their services to customers on a broader basis. In Europe, however, 5G remains a goal more than a reality (see Figure 2: 5G subscribers (in thousands) across geographic regions

Figure 2: 5G subscribers (in thousands) across geographic regions³

According to GSMA, the first stage of 5G investments corresponds to early deployments between 2018 and 2020, with USD 140 bn spent in the US, South Korea, Japan, and China. The five largest European countries will contribute USD 30 bn and Gulf Corporation Council (GCC) players will spend roughly USD 5 bn. Over the next five years, APAC will spend almost USD 400 bn, and Europe will spend roughly USD 200 bn.

The COVID-19 pandemic is not thought to have had a significant impact on these CAPEX figures. Although the pandemic delayed some 2020 investment into 2021, most experts believe investment will proceed as planned during the next half-decade.

¹ ADL analysis based upon publicly available information from operators: Rakuten claims to have 40% savings in OPEX and 30% savings in CAPEX using vRAN, China Mobile 53% opex and 30% CAPEX with savings in power consumption, site rental fees on site management and repairs and T Mobile reports that vRAN can reduce CAPEX for 5G by up to 50% compared with 4G.

² Publicly available information from operators, ADL analysis

³ <https://fr.idate.org/produit/5g-markets-in-europe-dataset-report/>

In Europe, 5G coverage is very limited so far, with a small number of base stations compared those of front runners such as South Korea, Japan, and China. The more advanced countries include Germany (in which e.g. Deutsche Telekom announced 50 percent 5G population coverage in July 2020), Switzerland (Swisscom achieved 90 percent population coverage by the end of 2019, and fellow Swiss MNO Sunrise had already achieved 80 percent as of August 2019), the Netherlands, and Finland. In Italy, rollouts began in 2019, with Vodafone announcing its first launch in five of the largest Italian cities and Wind Tre followed.

Elsewhere in Europe, rollouts are less advanced. As of September 2020, more than half of the European Union's 27 member countries had not yet launched 5G commercial services.⁴ Most obviously absent is France, which, as of October 2020, had still not launched any 5G services. This is hardly surprising, given the government had only hosted its spectrum auction in September 2020 and MNOs had not yet had time to organize full-scale rollouts.

Across industry experts, the same story is heard: MNOs are struggling to find the right business case for 5G, because of its strength in 4G. Consumers are indifferent toward higher broadband speeds, and business use cases have not yet been fully explored. Thus, rollouts have primarily remained localized public relations affairs, with operators racing to be the first to rollout in each city.

2.2 High spectrum prices and lack of cohesion and scale in public initiatives

As of September 2020 just 25.5 percent of 5G spectrum had been released in Europe and price variations are high: Italian 5G rollouts began with a spectrum auction that raised an eye-watering EUR 6.55 bn (\$0.4 per MHz pop), EUR 4.35 bn of which came from the auction of 200 MHz of 3.7 GHz airwaves. The UK's auction saw a price of \$0.17 per MHz pop, while in Spain and Ireland the price paid was well below \$0.10 per MHz pop. German auctions were also priced highly, with operators paying \$0.20 per MHz pop.

Mobile average revenue per user (ARPU) has been declining or remained flat in all regions (-14.4 percent globally between 2012 and 2017), and is much lower in Europe than in North America (see Figure 3) as a result of high levels of competition and a lack of consolidation in the market. Although lower ARPU in APAC, operating costs are also lower, which offsets some of the difference in revenue. Perhaps more importantly, leading APAC countries have received significant support for rollouts through government initiatives, which has not been as forthcoming in Europe.

Figure 3: Mobile ARPU by region, EUR/month⁵

Despite some worthwhile to mention national investment programmes in the UK (EUR 834 million to 5G trials), Germany (EUR 180 million “Gigabit Germany Initiative” and “5G Initiative for Germany”) and Finland (EUR 467 million of funding for R&I), Europe has lagged behind in terms of national 5G development programs and there has been little guidance or direction from the European Union. The largest investment (EUR 3.5 billion, thereof 700 million of public investment) stemming from the European 5G Infrastructure Public Private

⁴ <https://www.wsj.com/articles/europe-is-falling-behind-on-5g-rollout-top-companies-warn-11600408801>

⁵ IDATE DigiWorld, State of Telecom Services & Players Worldwide, December 2018

Partnership (5G-PPP), pale in comparison to those in APAC. China's government initiatives plan to invest over USD 150 billion by 2025 in 5G networks, which will dwarf any other countries' investments.⁶ In South Korea, the Korean government and 5G Forum, a public-private partnership, defined the 5G mobile strategy as early as January 2014, and allocated USD 1.5 billion, a huge figure for a country with a population of roughly 50mn as of 2020.

The slow pace of deployment of new infrastructure in Europe is a result of a lack of investment from both MNOs and governmental institutions. This is exacerbated by the lack of enough synergies between national and European initiatives supporting 5G, as well as of coordination among spectrum policies. Not only does this lead to significant differences in development speed among countries (e.g., Germany versus France), but it also enlarges the gap between Europe and the rest of the world.

2.3 Market size and vendor landscape

Against the background of 5G rollouts, the global 4G and 5G infrastructure market is estimated to be valued at USD 56 bn, 70 percent of which is found in the target geographies of the study. Of this, roughly 35 percent is found in the services, maintenance, installation costs, set-up fees and COTS hardware associated with establishing and operating a mobile network, none of which are within the scope of our study. The remaining 65 percent is the USD 25.4 bn that has been calculated.

Over 50 percent of the global 4G / 5G infrastructure market is covered within the US, China, and the EU-27. The EU market is valued at USD 4.71 bn, smaller than China and the US, which are valued at USD 10.64 bn and 6.17, respectively (see Figure 3).

The spread of spending across RAN, Core, Transport and DC, and OSS is roughly equal across the major geographies, though there are often notable differences between the ratios spent on 4G and 5G within individual domains. These can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Global 4G / 5G market across geographies⁷

The analysis showed that the EU-27 Infrastructure market, which has the least dynamic growth expectation until 2025 is heavily dominated by Huawei, Ericsson and Nokia. Experts estimate that in 2019, Huawei had 28 percent of Europe's total mobile infrastructure market, with Ericsson on 27 percent and Nokia on 23 percent.⁸

Within the 4G and 5G RAN infrastructure market specifically, the trend continues, with Huawei leading, Ericsson a close second, and Nokia in third place. ZTE commands less than 10 percent of the RAN market. Their combined RAN market share is roughly 90 percent. Huawei's strength in Europe is built on its support for not only 4G and 5G, but also legacy network systems. By providing "single RAN" systems at low prices,

⁶ <https://www.rcrwireless.com/20190702/5g/china-invest-over-150-billion-5g-networks-2025-report>

⁷ Arthur D. Little analysis, expert interviews

⁸ <https://www.lightreading.com/5g/ericsson-huawei-and-nokias-5g-wins-are-no-big-deal/a/d-id/757677>

Huawei became a crucial vendor in many MNOs' networks during the 4G era. On an aggregated European scale, "new kids" are a very small percentage of the market (less than 3 percent).

The US market for 4G and 5G infrastructure is second only to China in scale. Within the US market, there is a lack of Chinese vendors in the US RAN market – Huawei only takes 5 percent of the Antenna Systems market share (compared with 32% in the EU-27), and ZTE is hardly present in the market at all. Of course, the weakness of Chinese vendors has been exacerbated by US posturing and security concerns, but also reflects longer-term preference in the US for companies to use American or European suppliers instead of Chinese ones. Ericsson and Nokia together command roughly 80 percent of the market. The US is also one of the leading proponents of ORAN, with all leading MNOs looking to find cheaper and "homegrown" alternatives to expensive European options. As such, Altiostar takes a 5 percent cut of total 5G basebands revenue, and Mavenir takes 6 percent. It is one of the few geographies in which we see a "new kid" claiming any market share in Antenna Systems.

China is by far the largest market globally in terms of infrastructure spending, over double the size of EU market. China spends over USD 10 bn per year – hence why China is so advanced in its 5G rollout plans. In RAN, we see the relative strength of homegrown RAN vendors Huawei and ZTE, which have long been awarded the bulk of network contracts, leaving a smaller share for Ericsson and Nokia. Overall, Huawei and ZTE have shouldered most of China's 5G push for 2020, as they secured most orders to build 5G base stations for China Mobile, China Unicom and China Telecom, the country's three key carriers.

2.4 Development perspectives

For now, the current 4G and 5G infrastructure market remains primarily dominated by four incumbent firms: Ericsson, Huawei, Nokia, and ZTE. These four firms all offer end-to-end solutions and a full swathe of infrastructure components. Samsung, the South Korean technology giant and a more recent entrant to the vendor market, along with the "new kids on the block", does not yet offer end-to-end solutions across networks (Samsung is close but lacks support for legacy 2G and 3G infrastructure).

In addition to those 4 + 1, "new kids on the block" are comparatively small companies that are disrupting the traditional vendor market through innovative products or sets of products. Typically, these are software-based ORAN products, designed to run on COTS hardware. Altiostar, Mavenir, Parallel Wireless and Affirmed are four of the largest.

For MNO disaggregation of hardware and software in combination with subsequent network function virtualization allows moving toward greater vendor diversity and ultimately raises the strategic question of whether to buy pre-integrated solutions from traditional network equipment providers or to source highly specialized IT-based solutions from upcoming "new kids on the block".

As of 2020, new vendors are more challenged than they claim in their RFPs – they compete on cost, and often vastly underestimate the volume of equipment an MNO will have to purchase from them to achieve the same capabilities as a traditional system. However, an increasing presence of new players in the infrastructure is likely to become visible over the next five years, as can be seen in the estimates of Figure 5. Based on IHS market data – new players almost double in market share, from roughly 4 percent in 2019 to 7 percent in 2025.

Figure 5: Core and RAN market-share forecasts⁹

Since the technology is not yet fully mature, in 2020 new players are predominantly involved in government and MNO pilot schemes. Although every major MNO is testing the equipment of “new kids”, none have implemented any rollouts. This offers time for traditional vendors to respond: either embrace the new technology or prepare to fight it. Huawei and Ericsson are already beginning to raise concern around security in a disaggregated network. However, as ORAN technology advances, they will begin to play a greater role in large-scale rollouts across the world. Particularly with the current political uncertainty surrounding Huawei, these new vendors will be fundamental to increasing innovation in a market with few players, as well as ensuring that prices remain low through competition.

However, among experts there is little doubt of the direction in which the market is moving, albeit slowly. Deutsche Telekom Germany is seeking to deploy ORAN for an entire city by the end of 2021. Given the potential for restrictions on Huawei, diversification is paramount for European and American operators, which will do all they can to hurry the development of “new kids”.

In fact, almost all the “new kids” are US companies. There are few European “new kids”. This, combined with the US’s intent to establish a presence in the market, is a concern for a Europe that wishes to remain at the forefront of the telecoms landscape, but witnesses a decline of European vendors. The desire of Europe’s buyers of radio network solutions to evade a potential lack of choice among very few suppliers is a key driver for their interest in continuing to use and buy from Chinese vendors. It is also of concern that any new US players will not behave noticeably differently to Chinese vendors from a cyber security perspective. Thus, if US players manage to establish a strong position in the market, this may be dismal for Nokia and add a challenge for Ericsson, while not improving cyber security risks.

Overall, concern over the decline of European vendors is widespread across experts and there is agreement that if it wants to keep up, Europe needs to be more forward thinking in terms of fostering an environment that supports and promotes technology and digitalization, while championing its infrastructure providers.

For Europe, increased global competition, and the broader vendor landscape that comes hand in hand with a shift toward ORAN, represents both a challenge to its vendors and an opportunity for the broader market. On the one hand, it would likely depress vendor profit margins, which are required for investment into R&D. Without them, technological development would slow, and European vendors might lose their current market-leading positions. On the other hand, there is an opportunity for new European players to enter the market. Perhaps more importantly, increased technological innovation is likely to drive down prices for MNOs and enable faster rollouts of 5G in Europe. Europe collectively needs a plan of action to juggle these dual objectives. Without one, Europe’s future at the forefront of telecoms could be at stake.

⁹ DNB Markets illustration based on IHS Market data. NB: percentages do not add up to 100% due to rounding.

3 MAIN MESSAGES FROM THE ANALYSIS OF OPEN INITIATIVES

In the analysis of open initiatives, we investigated the current state of play in standardization, followed by the most promising open RAN initiatives specifying the APIs for interfaces and logical splits of the 5G NR RAN defined by the 3GPP¹⁰. Then, we analysed which 4G/5G deployments and trails have been already conducted towards an open RAN.

Figure 6: Initiatives and project groups focusing on the specification of APIs and solutions for an open RAN in 5G.

In order to identify the most promising and impactful Open RAN initiatives we look at who initially founded them, and how the initiatives evolved over the past years. We also differentiated the open initiatives based on their focus (see Figure 6):

- Project groups around the Telecom Infra Project (TIP)¹¹ focus on working towards integrated products or solutions, whereas initiatives like the O-RAN Alliance¹² focus on providing open specifications of APIs defined by the 3GPP in Rel. 15 & Rel. 16 (5G NR) and developing own specifications. The Open RAN Policy Coalition promotes policies that will advance the adoption of open and interoperable solutions in the RAN.¹³
- Small Cell Forum has been very successful in specifying and promoting their (network) functional application platform interface ((n)FAPI) for previous “G”s such as, 3G and 4G LTE, which is also being specified for 5G NR, more explicitly for the logical/functional split option 6 of 3GPP.
- Initially the Cloud RAN (C-RAN) initiative, kicked off by China Mobile Research, and xRAN, a group formed in 2016 with the goal to develop, standardize and promote an open alternative to the traditionally closed, hardware-based RAN architecture mainly initiated by Cisco, have been the predecessors of the promising O-RAN Alliance. Thus, it is key to understand that most of the initiatives operate on a global scale.

Although driven by the mainstream vendors and telecom operators these initiatives specify open APIs for several split options defined in 5G NR, aiming on a disaggregation of the RAN. Thereby, we want to emphasize that “open APIs” shall not be confused with “open source”, meaning these APIs are open to others (for use) but disclosed in their source code and maybe also in their service quality. This openness of APIs does not

¹⁰ 3GPP TR 38.801 (V14.0.0), Study of new radio access technology: Radio access architecture and interfaces

¹¹ <https://telecominfraproject.com/>

¹² <https://www.o-ran.org/>

¹³ <https://www.openranpolicy.org/>

mean that there is no business model behind it. Opening APIs may not limit their functionality, but vendors may implement different levels of Quality of Service (QoS) at which they serve requests based on their business model.

3.1 The state of play of international standardisation activities: 3GPP and ETSI

For network industries, interface standards, which assure the compatibility between the different components of the network, are the necessary requirement for the development of the network and the exploitation of network effects. Providers of network technologies are interested in influencing the specification of future network technologies, which will generate a competitive advantage against competing technologies and their providers. The evolution of standard-essential patents (SEPs) shows that patent families related to the 5G standardisation activities are increasing at a linear growth path (Pohlmann et al. 2020¹⁴) and that the number of patent owners has been increased to more than 100. Top 5G related patent owners are also those being strongly represented in the 5G market, i.e. Huawei Technologies (CN) taking the lead, followed by Samsung (KR), ZTE Corporation (CN), LG Electronics (KR), Nokia (incl. Alcatel-Lucent) FI, and Ericsson (SE).

Concerning the future evolution of 5G, our screening of international standardisation activities showed that mostly 3GPP is relevant for RAN standards, with other groups like ISO, IEC, ITU and IEEE only having limited relevance.

The **3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP)** unites seven telecommunications standard development organizations (ARIB, ATIS, CCSA, ETSI, TSDSI, TTA, TTC), known as “Organizational Partners” and provides their members with a stable environment to produce the Reports and Specifications that define 3GPP technologies. The project covers cellular telecommunications technologies, including radio access, core network and service capabilities, which provide a complete system description for mobile telecommunications. Real progress on 3GPP standards is measured by the milestones achieved in Releases.

Release 16 is a major release for the project, not least because it brings the International Mobile Telecommunication (IMT) 2020 submission for an initial full 3GPP 5G system to its completion (see <https://www.3gpp.org/release-16>). As part of Release 16, Mobile Communication (MC) services are extended to address a wider business sector than the initial rather narrow public security and civil defence services for which they had originally been developed. If the same or similar standards can be used for commercial applications (from taxi dispatching to railway traffic management, and other vertical sector scenarios currently being investigated), this would bring enhanced reliability to those -MC services through wider deployment, and reduced deployment costs due to economies of scale – to the benefit of all users.

ETSI, a European Standards Organization (ESO), is the EU recognized regional standards body dealing with telecommunications, broadcasting and other electronic communications networks and services. ETSI supports European regulations and legislation through the creation of Harmonised European Standards.

5G Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV), which is a key technology enabler for 5G (<http://etsi.org/nfv/>) - is a core area of activity of ETSI. 5G networks are anticipated to take advantage of Cloud-native principles for the design of some of their network functions (e.g. to facilitate scaling and healing) and the NFV Industry Specification Group (ISG) is developing a specification of criteria to help characterize such functions. Therefore, ETSI 1) is developing a report aimed at documenting how 5G network slicing use cases can be mapped to current NFV concepts and supported by the ETSI NFV architectural framework; 2) has initiated a project to develop an Open Source NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) software stack aligned with ETSI NFV - <http://osm.etsi.org/> 3) develops specifications to support placing computational functionality in networks closer to the end user, which will reduce latency in a range of 5G applications, and is developing standards for monitoring and controlling power consumption in 5G networks (TC EE), a significant factor in the viability of 5G, both economically and environmentally.

¹⁴ Pohlmann, Tim; Blind, Knut; Heß, Philipp (2020): Fact finding study on patents declared to the 5G standard, report on behalf of the German Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy

ETSI's new group on Experiential Networked Intelligence (ENI) will help operators leverage Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques and 5G will also be underpinned by an evolution of network protocols, an area explored by ETSI's ISG on Next Generation Protocols (NGP). The advent of 5G will also require fresh approaches to the efficient use of finite spectrum resources to meet projected growth in media-rich traffic. ETSI continues to explore improvements in spectral efficiency and advances in spectrum-sharing techniques. Of interest to 5G operators are yet unexploited radio frequencies in the millimetre wave band. This is an area being explored by the ETSI ISG on millimetre Wave Transmission (mWT).

3.2 The analysis of open initiatives

In the analysis of the ongoing open RAN initiatives and specifications, we investigated the most promising ongoing RAN initiatives and provided insights on which functional splits of 5G NR they are focusing. We spoke with selected experts from industry and academia to ensure a third-party perspective and we also identified the maturity level of the manifold specifications provided by these initiatives which, in some cases, target different functional/logical splits of the RAN. These findings are illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 7: 5G NR interfaces targeted by different initiatives with their estimated TRL level (Source: own illustration based on O-RAN alliance white paper “O-RAN: Towards an Open and Smart RAN” and amended with own research)“.

In technical terms, the **O-RAN Alliance**¹⁵ (together with the O-RAN software community¹⁶) is leading in terms of being the enabler for a change towards an open RAN. However, there are still many open questions, especially with respect to performance in different dimensions and use cases of 5G NR. Currently, most of the test deployments cover the Enhanced Mobile Broadband use case but do only pay a small attention to Ultra Reliable and Low Latency Communications. From a technical point of view some of the specifications of the interfaces/APIs have reached a high maturity level and will probably only take another year to reach a significant maturity level. Nevertheless, from a commercial point of view it may take up to 3 years in order to manifest the APIs in products and real-world large-scale deployments.

The O-RAN Alliance reuses and adopts the principles and protocol stack of the interfaces E1, F1, X2 and Xn, defined by the 3GPP, and also defines new open interfaces such as A1, E2, O1, O2 and the open fronthaul (currently the focus is on split 7-2x). The most interesting interfaces are the X2 and the open fronthaul interfaces. The former provides the logical and functional connection between eNodeBs and the latter allows

¹⁵ <https://www.o-ran.org/about>

¹⁶ <https://o-ran-sc.org/>

that RRH and DUs can be separated and therefore opens the market even for small and medium enterprises (SMEs).

The question that we face here, is how SMEs will set foot in this market and how well they will stand their ground. The open RAN provides possibility to develop business models based on the Quality of Service (QoS) that APIs deliver. Although open RAN may result in commoditised plug-and-play hardware, it may not be commercially viable for the equipment vendors to fully open source the underlying software. Effectively parts of the equipment supply chain are likely to remain a 'black box'. Here the question arises on how to ensure interoperability and guaranteed performance.

The **Small Cell Forum (SCF)**¹⁷ consists of three leadership members and executive members from AT&T, BAI Communications, Cellnex, Crown Castle, Dense Air, Jio, Nokia and Qualcomm. The SCF situates itself as complementary initiative to 3GPP, O-RAN, ETSI, TIP and Wireless Broadband Alliance (WBA).

The 5G FAPI suite of specifications are a part of the initiative from Small Cell Forum to promote widespread adoption of small cells for different deployment scenarios. The key benefit of 5G nFAPI specification is that it enables vendors providing base stations and radio solutions for small cells to adopt a distributed and disaggregated architecture by introducing a network interface between L2+ layers and a radio unit hosting PHY and RF components.

The 5G nFAPI specification is **an evolution** of the LTE nFAPI protocol to accommodate the needs of 5G NR. nFAPI concepts, framework and interfaces remain the same. Future development perspectives made by SCF indicate that further releases of 5G nFAPI are planned to address messages specific to P19 (RF and digital front-end control) and P4 (network monitoring) interfaces. The FAPI suite of specifications will also be updated to support 3GPP Rel. 16 features.

The **technological maturity level** is determined in terms of TRL which is for this specification approximately TRL 6-7. The API is very evolved and is a successor of previous successful APIs and, thus, highly likely to be adopted by the industry. Intel did already implement the FAPI specification into their FlexRAN solution which is a reference implementation for cloud enabled wireless access VNFs, which is also available on github¹⁸.

3.3 Possible obstacles of Open RAN

Open RAN potentially offers different benefits including vendor diversity and interoperability, flexibility, network automation, faster time to market with services, as well as the possibility of new software and hardware players on the market.¹⁹ However, there are still open issues and obstacles concerning the future development of Open RAN.

3.3.1 Massive MIMO

One point of discussion is massive MIMO, a key technology of 5G, in Open RAN. In a recent article²⁰ different analysts commented on the availability of Open RAN massive MIMO for near future deployments. Some of the comments claim that for rural areas, where coverage is critical, Open RAN technologies can be deployed to reduce overall costs. In dense urban areas, however, where network capacity is an issue, complex technologies like massive MIMO require vendor optimized networks (vertically integrated RAN) that cannot yet be supported by Open RAN technologies (due to requirements on the synchronisation between (distributed) massive MIMO base stations, bandwidth requirements of massive MIMO between RU and DU, and depending on the employed functional split²¹). Samsung e.g. does not commit to have a fully blown open RAN support in its massive MIMO product portfolio. On the other hand, Nokia claimed that its new product will support massive

¹⁷ <https://www.smallcellforum.org/about-us/>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/intel/FlexRAN>

¹⁹ https://www.rcrwireless.com/20200925/open_ran/breaking-down-the-pros-of-open-ran

²⁰ <https://www.lightreading.com/open-ran/open-ran-might-not-be-ready-for-americas-big-5g-push/d/d-id/765090>

²¹ <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/architecture-and-technology/silicon-photonics/5g-fronthaul-network-architectures-paper.html>

MIMO and the Open RAN specifications for fronthaul interfaces. Ericsson, according to the article developed a range of massive MIMO products that will support the C-Band spectrum in the US (3.7 – 4.2 GHz), but the question if those products adhere to Open RAN specifications was not addressed. Nevertheless, recently e.g. NEC and Analog Devices announced that they have teamed up to design a 5G Network Massive MIMO Antenna Radio Unit for Rakuten Mobile that possesses a 5G open vRAN interface.²² Furthermore, in October the O-RAN alliance conducted a plugfest where AltioStar, NEC as well as Bharti Airtel²³ teamed up and focused specifically on interoperability testing and integration of massive MIMO radio units on and virtualised distributed units running on common-off-the-shelf (COTS) servers.

3.3.2 Security

Open RAN is mainly about disaggregation and virtualization of radio access network core functions. It provides the opportunity of handling the massive amount of data while increasing the return on invest in CAPEX and OPEX infrastructure costs²⁴. However, in comparison to a fully vertical integrated RAN, this introduces new dimensions of security risks and threats. With a fully virtualized RAN several new security threats come up, that can be investigated from different point of views:

- From a customer side one has to deal with the 11 security threats of cloud computing²⁵ (i.e., data breach, misconfiguration and inadequate change control, insufficient identity and credential management, account hijacking, weak control plane, etc.) for which solutions exist but adds another layer of complexity to the virtualization framework.
- More important are the security threats and vulnerabilities which arise from the employed virtualization framework²⁶ such as, i.e., VM hopping, malicious insider, data leakage, data loss, co-location/co-resident attacks, etc.

Some of these security issues may be solved but there also exist others, hardware-based security issues such as attacks like Meltdown²⁷, Spectre and Spectre-Next-Generation which cannot easily be overcome by patching software. These security threats are very delicate with respect to the ambitious goal of virtualizing the whole RAN on common-off-the-shelf hardware. It seems that the O-RAN Alliance has ignored these issues until March 2020 and finally created the “Security Task Group” in October 2020. This task group shall address the new threat surface that is created by the disaggregation of RAN functions. The effort tries to integrate security into open RAN instead of adding it on-top. This already points in the right direction but many interfaces are already specified and therefore it is questionable how well security (especially with respect to the previously discussed threats and vulnerabilities) can be integrated into open RAN. Even then, it is unclear how telecom providers will address security threats which cannot be handled by the specifications (i.e. hardware-based security attacks).

3.4 Development perspectives

Open RAN encompasses a wide range of technologies and includes all stakeholders in the telecoms sector, making the analysis of its current state complex and heterogeneous. The findings from the expert interviews

²² <https://www.eedesignit.com/5g-o-ran-massive-mimo-radio-for-rakuten-mobile/>

²³ <https://www.rcrwireless.com/20201113/network-function-virtualization-nfv/altioStar-nec-demo-massive-mimo-at-o-ran-alliance-event-in-india>

²⁴ For an analysis of its feasibility see: X. Costa-Perez, J. Swetina, T. Guo, R. Mahindra and S. Rangarajan, "Radio access network virtualization for future mobile carrier networks," in IEEE Communications Magazine, vol. 51, no. 7, pp. 27-35, July 2013, doi: 10.1109/MCOM.2013.6553675.

²⁵ Cloud Security Alliance. Top Threats to Cloud Computing. <http://www.cloudsecurityalliance.org>

²⁶ O. AbdElRahem, A. M. Bahaa-Eldin and A. Taha, "Virtualization security: A survey," 2016 11th International Conference on Computer Engineering & Systems (ICCES), Cairo, 2016, pp. 32-40, doi: 10.1109/ICCES.2016.7821971.

²⁷ Moritz Lipp, Michael Schwarz, Daniel Gruss, Thomas Prescher, Werner Haas, Anders Fogh, Jann Horn, Stefan Mangard, Paul Kocher, Daniel Genkin, Yuval Yarom, Mike Hamburg, „Meltdown: Reading kernel memory from user space“, 27th {USENIX} Security Symposium ({USENIX} Security, 2018

suggest that open RAN adoption will be highly dependent on whether cost advantages to the operators can be realised, which is not yet certain.

Open RAN could potentially increase the number of options concerning the choice of equipment suppliers for the network operators. However, it remains very unclear whether companies that exited the network equipment business (e.g. Alcatel, Siemens, or Motorola) due to high costs, low margins, and competition from Asian suppliers, would be interested to re-enter the market.

Although network virtualisation solutions could be used in commoditised hardware based on Open RAN, the network virtualisation solutions may not be interoperable. This observation is likely to be crucial when the operator preference for cloud-native RAN is considered. Interoperability between high-profile cloud service providers such as Amazon Web Services, Microsoft Azure, or Google Compute is not yet well-established.²⁸ This suggests that in the absence of backend interoperability in network virtualisation solutions, commoditised hardware may not help the operators effectively reduce lock-in with specific network equipment suppliers. Some experts highlighted that operators could end up swapping their dependence from specific network equipment suppliers to virtualisation solution providers or cloud platform providers.

Experts also cautioned against Open RAN initiatives being a solution to perceived security issues in network equipment, or as an enabler of more diverse, resilient supply chains. Although Open RAN initiatives may lead to more choices of network equipment suppliers (e.g. beyond Nokia, Ericsson and Huawei), this overlooks the market dependence on one or two suppliers of chipsets (e.g. Intel or Qualcomm).

Inclusion of Open RAN-based equipment from multiple suppliers in conjunction with existing base stations and equipment (including based on 3GPP interfaces) may also increase operator costs on system integration and maintenance. It is not yet clear who will take the responsibility for integration and maintenance when multiple vendors provide equipment and software. We further see the problem of know-how transfer, as operators may not have the resources to acquire the needed know-how. This can potentially increase the cost of ownership for the operators and significantly impact their return on investment.

The complexity of the existing supply chains and the role of economies of scale in network deployment are likely to be key factors in how effective Open RAN initiatives will be when considered in conjunction with the performance of Open RAN-based equipment on key technical parameters such as network reliability, energy efficiency, and effective support for (massive) MIMO methods.

We also see a shortcoming on the European market, as if open RAN takes off there will be a shift from a single vendor supplied RAN to a multi-vendor RAN which is currently targeted by many companies originated in the US and Asia. There are only few European companies (e.g. Accelleran²⁹, Benetel³⁰, Maven³¹) in the Open RAN initiatives.

Adoption of Open RAN holds important implications for traditional equipment vendors such as Nokia and Ericsson. Both companies have been heavily invested in implementing 3GPP specifications. Ericsson appears to have taken a more cautious approach towards Open RAN since its inception. However, both organisations have become actively involved with Open RAN. This suggests that the communications industry consensus about the potential of Open RAN and the role it could play in the network equipment may be changing. In comparison with Ericsson, Nokia appears to have been more open in its approach to the development of Open RAN specifications³². However, Ericsson is a member of the O-RAN alliance since 2019 and has a main focus

²⁸ See Martino, Beniamino Di, Giuseppina Cretella, and Antonio Esposito. 2015. *Cloud Portability and Interoperability: Issues and Current Trends*. Springer Briefs in Computer Science. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-13701-8> for a more detailed discussion on interoperability challenges in cloud service platforms

²⁹ <https://www.accelerant.com/>

³⁰ <https://benetel.com/>

³¹ <https://mavenwireless.com/>

³² <https://www.lightreading.com/5g/nokia-is-first-big-kit-vendor-to-unveil-o-ran-suite/d/d-id/761884>

in O-RAN in RAN intelligence and automation. Given the market share and the size of annual R&D investments of Nokia and Ericsson, their continued participation could prove a decisive factor in the future of Open RAN.

In the long-term, the adoption and growth of open RAN is likely to be driven by whether it offers market gains for incumbent or any new equipment suppliers, its implications for the total cost of ownership and return on investment for the operators, whether the diversification of the network equipment supply chain will extend to other aspects of network such chipsets, cloud platforms, and virtualisation solutions available to operators.